

Extended Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika Ontology as Applied to Amarakośa KnowledgeNet

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Abstract. *Amarakośa* is a thesaurus which provides list of words to the concepts categorised based on different domain and context. Knowledge in this kośa concerns with many non-observational and culture specific facts that connect many concepts within and outside the domain. In this paper we present a few representative examples of the concept clusters from *Amarakośa* KnowledgeNet (A-KN) where the extended *Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika* (NV) ontology is applied. We will also show how the knowledge base of *Amarakośa* requires an extension for NV ontology when we tried to apply the same.

Key-words: Ontology, *Amarakośa*, *jāti*, *upādhi*, *jātibādhakās*

1 Introduction

Indian tradition of transmitting knowledge orally is on the verge of vanishing. As the oral transmission demands, Indian traditional educational culture was organized to be ‘formal and intensive’ as opposed to the modern culture which is more ‘informal and extensive’ (Wood, 1985). The close inspection of the structure of the *Amarakośa* gives much more insight into the way the words are organized. When a student memorizes it, though in the beginning it appears as a linear list of words, as he starts understanding the meaning of the words, reads the commentaries on this text and starts using these words, the linear structure unfolds into a knowledge web with various links.

In this paper, we present a few examples from the *Amarakośa* KnowledgeNet Ver.0.1 (Nair, 2010), which necessitated the extension of NV ontology when it was applied. Any knowledge structure involved with many concepts and the relations needs an ontological system in its base. Without a sound ontological grounding, building a knowledge structure on top of it may create problems. In order to provide a strong base, we chose NV ontological system for building

Amarakośa KnowledgeNet. When the ontological systems applied, we find many incompletions and inconsistencies. To get rid of them, an extended ontology on the basis of NV system is developed. In this process many ideas from other disciplines are also taken care.

2 Amarakośa

Amarakośa primarily named as *Nāmaṅgānuśāsana* (a work that deals with instructions related to the gender of nouns) is authored by *Amarasimha* - 4th century A.D. (Oka, 1981) - and is the most celebrated and authoritative ancient thesaurus of Sanskrit with around 60 commentaries and translations into modern Indian as well as foreign languages such as Chinese, Tibetan, French, etc. (Patkar, 1981). It consists of 1608 verses composed in *anuṣṭup* meter and are divided into 3 chapters called *kāṇḍas*.

3 Ontology for A-KN

The word ‘Ontology’ with Greek origin means “the study of being or existence or reality’. The study of existence of entities, their classification based on similarities or differences, and the hierarchy involved in it, is very close to the philosophical studies. Historically, ontologies arise out of the branch of philosophy known as metaphysics, which deals with the nature of reality of what exists. Ontology also plays an important role in Knowledge Representation which is a way of specification or representation of a concept. J. F. Sowa explains - “The subject of ontology is the study of the categories of things that exist or may exist in some domain” (J.F.Sowa,2000 p.492). The traditional goal of ontological inquiry in particular is to divide the world “at its joints”, to discover those fundamental categories, or kinds, into which the worlds objects naturally fall.

History of ontology records various traditional ontological schools. In the east, especially in India, each school of thought has developed its own ontology. Among the major ones, NV ontology is considered as prominent one as it is grounded on sound logic and widely applicable to any domain. Because of that nature, this ontology is admitted as the best candidate to govern the semantics of *Amarakośa*.

Many upper-level ontologies capture the relation between the concepts used in common human understanding are based on Western Ontology. It cannot be directly adopted to develop KnowledgeNet for Indian languages, especially for Sanskrit. The concepts like *svarga*, *viṣṇu*, *asura*, equipments of deities, animals of deities etc. cannot be accommodated in these upper-level ontologies. So we thought the necessity of make an upper-level ontology using Indian traditional Śāstras to accommodate the concepts that are specific to Indian languages and culture.

4 NV ontology

The choice of NV ontology for this purpose was on the base of simple reason, that NV ontology has a clear tree structure of categories that are based on experience of common people and it has also given scope for reasoning. *Nyāya* School of thought started by Gautama in 300 B.C, deals with the epistemology i.e. means of knowledge fallacies, art of debates, justifications etc. On the other hand *Vaiśeṣika* school, established by *Kaṇāda*, is a realistic school, which focuses on ontology of the whole world and the characteristics relations of the entities. Both these schools have merged into one stream with some additions and omissions by complementing each other. The new NV School reduced the total cosmic entities into seven *padārthas* or the ontological categories. They are *dravya* (substance), *guṇa* (quality), *karma* (motion), *sāmānya* (universal), *viśeṣa* (particularity), *samavāya* (inherence) and *abhāva* (negation).⁴ These are further subdivided. The details of each classification is given in appendix in Fig. 1.

5 NV categories

Among the seven categories, first three belong to the phenomenon world. Any common man through his senses can perceive substances, their qualities and action. Substance is the abode of the qualities and actions. Qualities are twenty four in number enumerated by NV system and actions or motions of different kinds are inherent in the substance which do not have independent existence. The substances both eternal and non-eternal are classified into nine.⁵ The other four categories are called *Śāstrik* categories, their existence is established by the reasons provided by *Śāstra*. Common-man without proper understanding of *Śāstra* cannot comprehend the notion of these categories. The notion of universals, inherence relation and particularities is inevitable for constructing NV system of ontology and making it whole and complete. The unique relation *samavāya* - inherence - gets the first three categories connected. The universals common properties of special kind put the entities in a common basket that show up in a tree-structure. The particularities on the other hand keep the entities belonging to common categories, unique and protect their individuality. Therefore, without these metaphysical notions, the whole and complete ontological system is impossible. The last category *abhāva* - absence - also finds an independent existence in the NV ontological system on par with the other being categories.

The core feature of this ontology is its wider applicability. The ontology is not just a prototype of the reality, rather it is a complete description of the real phe-

⁴ *Tarkasaṅgraha p.2*

⁵ *Pṛthvī* (earth), *āpaḥ* (water), *tejas* (fire), *vāyu* (air), *ākāśa* (ether), *kāla* (time), *dik* (direction), *ātman* (soul), *manas* (mind). (*Tarkasaṅgraha p.5*)

nomenon world. Hence the definitions and categories of any ontological system must find a consistent and clear application in the real objects of the world.

6 NV theory of universal

The NV theory of universal (*jāti*) does not recognize all general characteristics as universal. According to them the universal is a natural and eternal class-essence like *gotvam* (cowness), *ghaṭatvam* (potness) etc. which is permanent feature of a particular thing. Other general characteristics such as *unnatatvam* (tallness), *nīlatvam* (blueness) etc. which are adventitious features, are not universal but termed as ‘*upādhis*’. The properties that are not considered as universals for some reasons become *upādhis*.

6.1 The impediments or jātibādhakās

The logical basis for the distinction of *jāti* and *upādhi* is explained by *Udayana* by enumerating six ‘impediments’ called *jātibādhakāḥ*. Presence of anyone of these six is sufficient to disqualify a characteristic as an universal. The six impediments are described in *Muktāvalī* as *vyakteḥ abhedah*, *tulyatvam*, *saṅkaraḥ*, *anavasthitih*, *rūpahānīḥ* and *asambandhaḥ*.⁶

Vyakteḥ abhedah :: Any property that resides in a single object is not an universal. E.g. *ākāśa* being single, *ākāśatva*, a property of being *ākāśa* is not universal.

Tulyatvam :: Two general names which are the synonyms, and thus describe exactly same *padārtha* do not stand for different universals. E.g. *ghaṭatva* and *kalaśatva*. Here either *ghaṭatva* is a universal, or *kalaśatva* is a universal but not both, since both reside in the same set of individuals are indicating the same thing itself.

Saṅkara :: The cross-dividing properties which co-exist in some instances and also exclude one another in others are not to be recognized as universals. Consider the five elements *prthvī*, *jala*, *tejas*, *vāyu* and *ākāśa*. *Bhūtatva* (being an element) is a property that exists in all these five elements. Of these the first four have *mūrtatva* (mobility). Now the question is, should *mūrtatva* be considered as an universal? We know that other than the first four elements, even the *manas* is also *mūrta* and hence it has *mūrtatva*. So *mūrtatva* is located in *manas* and not in *ākāśa*. Similarly, *bhūtatva* exists in *ākāśa* excluding *manas*. Both *mūrtatva* and *bhūtatva* reside in four elements. Therefore, both these mutually exclusive properties have shared location. This situation leads to *saṅkara*. Hence both the properties are not considered as universals.

⁶ *vyakterabhedatulyatvam saṅkaro'thānavasthitih*.

rūpahānīrasambandhaḥ jātibādhakasaṅgrahaḥ.. (Muktāvalī - pratyakṣakhaṇḍa) p.25

Anavasthitih :: The character recognition of which as a universal, leads to infinite regress, means universality (*jātitva*) is not to be considered as *jāti*, it can be *upādhi*. If universality was regarded as a universal then another universality will be required to synthesis the former with the latter and this process becomes infinite. Therefore, the concept of universal is not to be regarded as corresponding to one more universal, namely, universality.

Rūpahāniḥ :: Ultimate difference cannot have any principle of unity, as it would contradict their essential nature (*viśeṣaṇāstu anantāḥ eva*). If *viśeṣatva* was regarded as an identity or universal, inhering in the *viśeṣas*, then mutual difference would not be there. *viśeṣas* being principles of ultimate differences, they cannot be differentiated from one another on the basis of any other characteristics. So *viśeṣatva* is also considered as *upādhi*.

Asambandhaḥ :: The universal by definition is, ‘inherent’ in its subject. This implies that the thing in which nothing can inhere cannot be the substrate of a universal. The categories of inherence (*samavāya*) and non-existence (*abhāva*) cannot have anything inhering in them. If *samavāyatva* is regarded as a universal, inhering in inherence, then it would have to inhere in both its substrate and its relation with it, which is absurd. Such a position would also lead to infinite regress. Hence, nothing can be conceived as inhering in inherence. Similarly, no universal can be conceived to inhere in negation, because, it is not a positive entity. Therefore, *samavāyatva* and *abhāvatva* are not to be regarded as universals.

Thus, these *jātibādhakas* impose constraints in the selection of *jātis*, and leads to multiple ways of classification. Choice of one way of classification forces other universal properties to be *upādhis*. This choice is typically guided by the application in hand. In what follows, we build the NV ontology further and provide detailed classification in order to edit suitable or application on *Amarakośa* KnowledgeNet.

7 Application of NV ontology on A-KN

The words of *Amarakośa* are categorized according to this scheme. Each *Amarakośa* entry is classified into a class which helped us to evolve the ontological classification just as an upper level ontology does. We followed both the top down as well as bottom up approach simultaneously in order to arrive at the ontological classification. For the top-down approach, though our starting point was *Vaiśeṣika* ontology, we deviated from it a bit. Further we have also introduced *upādhis* wherever the need arouse. While adopting *Vaiśeṣika* ontology to classify words in *Amarakośa*, it is noticed that, some of the classes (since there are no instances of those in the *Amarakośa*) are not needed, while we also required further sub-classification of some of them. Out of these *Amarakośa* has instances only corresponding to *dravya*, *guṇa*, *karma*, *sāmānya* and *abhāva*. By

this enterprise of applying NV ontology on *Amarakośa* has improved the A-KN in many aspects. Some of them are given below.

1. *Amarakośa* categories are brought into the classification of an ontological system.
2. The tree structure has given the scope for reasoning about the properties and relations of the categories.
3. With this application new types of *upādhis* have been emerged in the AKN. This has enhanced the understanding of *Amarakośa* categories.
4. On the other hand the limitation of the NV ontology is shown while its application on a world of real time categories.

Thus, these *jātibādhakas* impose constraints in the selection of *jātis*, and leads to multiple ways of classification. Choice of one way of classification forces other universal properties to be *upādhis*. This choice is typically guided by the application in hand where we build the NV ontology further and provide detailed classification, so that we can classify the *padārthas* in *Amarakośa*. The detailed description of this scheme is given below. The graphical representation is also given in appendix Fig.2 and 3.

The result in classification of *padārthas* in *Amarakośa* that emerged after the adaptation of NV ontology is shown in appendix Fig.2., where the additions or deletions of some of the nodes are justified. According to *Vaiśeṣika*, *padārtha* (reality) is the entity encompassing all things, viz. *dravya*, *guṇa*, *karma*, *sāmānya*, *viśeṣa*, *samavāya* and *abhāva* as classified into seven. Out of these, *Amarakośa* has instances only corresponding to *dravya*, *guṇa*, *karma*, *sāmānya* and *abhāva*. All those words which could not be classified are put under *śeṣaḥ*.

8 Dravya Classification

According to *Vaiśeṣika*, *dravya* is classified into nine viz. *ṛṥhvī*, *jala*, *tejas*, *vāyu*, *ākāśa*, *kāla*, *dik*, *manas* and *ātmā*, which are taken as it is in NV ontology. First eight elements are classified into *nitya* and *anitya* as well as *ātmā* into *jīvātmā* and *paramātmā*. Since we are looking at *Amarakośa* from NLP point of view, this classification does not give us much mileage. Hence we deviated a bit from *Vaiśeṣika* ontology and further sub-classified three of them viz. *ṛṥhvī*, *tejas* and *ātmā* as described below.

8.1 The sub-classes of *ṛṥhvī*

There are different kinds of elements which come under *ṛṥhvī* in *Amarakośa*. All the elements under *ṛṥhvī* are classified on the basis of two properties viz. *cala/acala* and *sajīva/nīrjīva*.⁷ In addition to the celestial elements, we have

⁷ These properties are not found in NV ontology. But these are added to accommodate the concepts found in *Amarakośa* for the chosen ontology

created one more node viz. *alaukika* to account celestial objects, we created the sub-nodes with *alaukika* only when there was an instance of the category with celestial object. The classification describing each node with definition and examples are given below. The number of sub-nodes is shown in parenthesis against each node.

pṛthvī (5)

- *calasajīvaḥ* (3)
 - the thing which is alive and mobile [E.g. *manuṣyaḥ*, *jantuḥ* etc.]
- *calanirjīvaḥ* (0)
 - the thing which is not alive but is mobile [E.g. *rathaḥ*, *ḍolā*, *pālakī* etc.]
- *alaukikacalanirjīvaḥ* (0)
 - the thing which is not alive, mobile and celestial [E.g. *puṣpakam*]
- *acalasaajīvaḥ* (7)
 - the thing which is alive and is not mobile [E.g. *vṛkṣaḥ*, *bhrūṇam* etc.]
- *acalanirjīvaḥ* (4)
 - the thing which is not alive and is not mobile [E.g. *chatram*, *mārgaḥ* etc.]

The sub-classes of *calasajīvaḥ*

The category *calasajīvaḥ* is classified into three as *manuṣyaḥ*, *manuṣyetaṛaḥ* and *alaukikacetanaḥ*. All these nodes contain qualities of the body, not of the soul.⁸ The classification is given here.

- *alaukikacetanaḥ* (0)
 - All the celestial beings [E.g. *Śacī*, *Aruṇaḥ* etc.]
- *manuṣyaḥ* (0)
 - human beings [E.g. *dhīvāraḥ*, *rājā* etc.]
- *manuṣyetaṛaḥ* (2)
 - non-human beings [E.g. *siṃhaḥ*, *matsyaḥ* etc.]

The sub-classes of *manuṣyetaṛaḥ*

Manuṣyetaṛaḥ node is classified into two viz. *jantuḥ* and *alaukikapṛāṇī*. The second node represents the celestial non-human beings. The *jantuḥ* node represents all non-human beings. The classification is given below.

- *jantuḥ* (6)
 - non-human living being [E.g. *sarpaḥ*, *kūṛmaḥ* etc.]
- *alaukikapṛāṇī* (0)
 - non-human celestial being [E.g. *airāvataṃ*, *garudaḥ* etc.]

The sub-classes of *jantuḥ*

- *jalīyaḥ* (0)
 - water body [E.g. *matsyaḥ*, *śankhaḥ* etc.]
- *ubhayacaraḥ* (0)

⁸ The human body comes under *pṛthvī* according to *Vaiśeṣika*

- the animals which can live in both water and earth [E.g. *maṇḍūkāḥ*, *kūrmāḥ* etc.]
- *sarīrpaḥ* (0)
 - reptiles [E.g. *sarpāḥ*, *sarāṭāḥ* etc.]
- *stanapāyī* (0)
 - mammals [E.g. *vānarāḥ*, *hiraṇāḥ* etc.]
- *pakṣī* (0)
 - birds [E.g. *śukāḥ*, *kākaḥ* etc.]
- *kṛtāḥ* (0)
 - insects [E.g. *jalaukāḥ*, *vṛścikāḥ* etc.]

The sub-classes of *acalasaṅgīvaḥ*

The node *acalasaṅgīvaḥ* classifies the plant world and non-moving living things. It is divided into seven categories as given below. The node *alaukikasasyaḥ* marks celestial plants.

- *acalasaṅgīvavastu* (0)
 - the living things which are not mobile. [E.g. *aṇḍam*, *kalalam* etc.]
- *vṛkṣāḥ* (0)
 - trees [E.g. *āmraḥ*, *kharjuraḥ* etc.]
- *latā* (0)
 - creepers [E.g. *mallikā*, *yūthikā* etc.]
- *oṣadhīḥ* (0)
 - shrubs [E.g. *nīlī*, *bākucī* etc.]
- *trṇam* (0)
 - grasses [E.g. *elā*, *jaṭāmāṁsī* etc.]
- *jalīyasasyaḥ* (0)
 - water plants [E.g. *padmam*, *kumudam* etc.]
- *alaukikasasyaḥ* (0)
 - celestial plants [E.g. *devavṛkṣāḥ*]

The sub-classes of *acalanirjīvaḥ*

Acalanirjīvaḥ node is classified into four, according to the necessities as follows.

- *alaukikācalanirjīvavastu* (0)
 - celestial non-living things which are not mobile [E.g. *viṣṇoḥ maṇīḥ* etc.]
- *sthānam* (3)
 - places [E.g. *mārgāḥ*, *nadī* etc.]
- *mūlakam* (0)
 - minerals [E.g. *abhrakam*, *pāradaḥ* etc.]
- *acalanirjīvavastu* (0)
 - non-living thing which are not mobile [E.g. *chatram*, *cāmaram* etc.]

8.2 The sub-classes of *sthānam*

- *alaukikasthānam* (0)
 - celestial places [E.g. *indravanam*, *kuberapurī* etc.]
- *mānavanirmitiḥ* (0)
 - places or things which are created by men [E.g. *kūpaḥ*, *mārgaḥ* etc.]
- *prākṛtikasthānam* (0)
 - natural places (not created by men) [E.g. *nadī*, *parvataḥ* etc.]

The extended classification of *pr̥thvī* shown above is to accommodate the concepts enumerated in the *Amarakośa*. One may note that this extension not only uses *jāti* but also the various *upādhis*. Without this extension with the mixture of *jāti* and *upādhi*, the A-KN cannot be described on the basis of an ontological scheme. NV ontology gives scope for both *jāti* and *upādhi*. Though it does not provide with an entry to *upādhis* in the tree constructed on the basis of *jāti*, this merging of two notions in one tree will not be contradictory.

8.3 The sub-classes of *tejas*

According to the *Vaiśeṣika* ontology *tejas* is divided into four viz. *bhauma*, *divya*, *udarya* and *ākaraḥ*, however, in this scheme *udarya* and *ākaraḥ* are considered under *bhauma*. *Tejas* is divided into *Bhauma* and *divya* in the present scheme. *Bhauma* again sub-divided into *dhātu* and *dahana*. The node *dahana* is divided into two viz. *śarīra* and *indhanaḥ*. The node *divya* has three divisions as *nakṣatra*, *graha* and *Vidyut*. The classification is given below.

bauma (2)

- *dhātu* (0)
 - all kinds of metals [E.g. *suvarṇam*, *rajatam* etc.]
- *dahana* (2)
 - fire [E.g. *agniḥ*, *yāgāgniḥ* etc.]
 - * *śarīraḥ* (0)
 - the fire produced in body [E.g. *gharmaḥ*]
 - * *indhanaḥ* (0)
 - the fire produced from fuel [E.g. *āhavanīyāgniḥ*, *saṁskṛtāgniḥ* etc.]

divya (3)

- *nakṣatra* (0)
 - all kinds of stars [E.g. *druvaḥ*, *kārtikā* etc.]
- *graha* (0)
 - all planets [E.g. *sūryaḥ*, *candraḥ* etc.]
- *vidyut* (0)
 - lightning [E.g. *vajrāgniḥ*, *taḍit* etc.]

8.4 The sub-classes of ātmā

Ātmā in *Vaiśeṣika* ontology is divided into two as *jīvātṃ* and *paramātṃ*. Ātmā can be classified as *siddhaḥ*, *sādhakaḥ* and *sāmānyaḥ*. *Sāmānya* can be classified into *devayoniḥ* and *manuṣyayoniḥ*. But in the present scheme *ātmā* is divided into four viz. *īśvaraḥ*, *devatā*, *ṛṣiḥ* and *devayoniḥ*. The category *siddhaḥ* is named as *devatā*, *sādhakaḥ* as *ṛṣiḥ* and *devayoniḥ* is taken as it is. In *Amarakośa* there is not a single entry which is related to *manuṣyayoni*. There are entries like *puruṣaḥ*, *strī* etc. are considered under the category named *manuṣyaḥ*, which comes under *pṛthivī*, because the gender etc. are *śārīrikaguṇas* (qualities of the body) of *manuṣya*, not *ātmaguṇas*. The classification is given below.

ātmā

- *īśvaraḥ* (0)
 - *trimūrtis* [E.g. *brahmā*, *viṣṇuḥ* and *maheśvaraḥ*]
- *devatā* (0)
 - all deities [E.g. *indraḥ*, *lakṣmī*, *yamaḥ* etc.]
- *ṛṣiḥ* (0)
 - sages [E.g. *buddhaḥ*, *agastyāḥ* etc.]
- *devayoniḥ* (0)
 - demi-gods or demons [E.g. *rākṣasaḥ*, *yakṣaḥ*, *kinnaraḥ* etc.]

9 Guṇa Classification

In the *Vaiśeṣika* ontology *guṇa* is classified into twenty four sub-divisions. The *Amarakośa* classification does not require all these divisions. The classes that are necessary to classify *Amarakośa* words are taken into consideration in this scheme. Some of the classes from *vaiśeṣika* ontology are merged into a single category. According to this scheme *guṇa* is classified into eight classes viz. *rūpam*, *rasaḥ*, *gandhaḥ*, *parimāṇam*, *śabdaḥ*, *buddhiḥ*, *adr̥ṣṭam* and *mānasikabhāvaḥ*. *Adr̥ṣṭam* marks both *dharma* and *adharmā*. The last class in this classification named as *mānasikabhāvaḥ* contains all kinds of mental feelings like *sukham*, *duḥkham*, *dveṣa* etc. The classification is given here.

guṇaḥ (7)

- *rūpam* (0)
 - colour [E.g. *śuklaḥ*, *nīlaḥ* etc.]
- *rasaḥ* (0)
 - taste [E.g. *madhura*, *amla* etc.]
- *gandhaḥ* (0)
 - smell [E.g. *sugandhaḥ*, *durgandhaḥ* etc.]
- *parimāṇam* (0)
 - measurements [E.g. *alpam*, *anekam* etc.]
- *śabdaḥ* (2)

- sound [E.g. *akṣaram, hastigarjanam* etc.]
- *buddhiḥ* (0)
 - intelligence [E.g. *buddhiḥ, jñānam* etc.]
- *adr̥ṣṭam* (0)
 - unforeseen merit or demerit [E.g. *dharmah, adharmah* etc.]
- *mānasikabhāvaḥ* (0)
 - mental condition [E.g. *icchā, sprhā* etc.]

9.1 The sub-classes of śabdaḥ

The node *śabda* is divided into two viz. *varṇātmakaḥ* and *dhvanyātmakaḥ*. *Varṇātmakaḥ* marks articulate sounds like letters etc. and *dhvanyātmakaḥ* marks all the instrumental sounds. *Varṇātmakaḥ* is divided into two viz. *apauruṣeyam* and *pauruṣeyam*. The node *apauruṣeyam* marks the divine knowledge which is available between the vedic time and the purāṇic time. The *pauruṣeyam* node represents the origin of other knowledge. The classification is given below.

- *varṇātmakaḥ* (2)
 - articulate sounds [E.g. *akṣaram* etc.]
 - * *apauruṣeyaḥ* (0)
 - divine knowledge [E.g. *vedāḥ, mantrāḥ* etc.]
 - * *pauruṣeyaḥ* (0)
 - the knowledge which are created by man [E.g. *vyākaraṇa, nyāya* etc.]
- *dhvanyātmakaḥ* (0)
 - instrumental sounds [E.g. *vīṇānādaḥ, tālaḥ* etc.]

10 Kriyā, sāmānya and abhāva classification

In *vaiśeṣika* ontology, *kriyā* is classified into five. Since *Amarakośa* does not have any instance of verbs, this class is not required. *Sāmānya* has two divisions as *param* and *aparam*. This scheme also adopted two sub-classes named *jātiḥ* and *avasthā*. *Jātiḥ* is the permanent property in all things but *avasthā* is the concurrent property. The words indicating absence are classified as *abhāvas*. Eg. *vr̥ṣṭyabhāvaḥ, vidyābhāvaḥ* etc..

11 Upādhi and its classification

Any property ie. qualified to be the universal as per the conditions* is considered as *upādhi*. The category of *upādhi* is an open list. Here in this scheme, the *upādhi* nodes are taken on the basis of necessity. *Upādhi* is divided into sixteen subclasses according to the A-KN. Some nodes have sub-divisions also. *Upādhi* nodes are - *avayavaḥ, samūhaḥ, vr̥ttiḥ, khādyam, nāma, vāhanam, vastram, upakaraṇam, ābharaṇam, ratnam, dhanam, ciḥnam, indriyam, kāraṇam, ākr̥tiḥ and śaktiḥ*. The classification is given in the appendix Fig.3. The classification describing each node with example is given below. The number of sub-nodes also shown in bracket against each node.

11.1 Upādhi classification

- *avayava* (0)
 - part of a living body [E.g. *phaṇaḥ*, *śākhā*, *pādaḥ* etc.]
- *samūhaḥ* (0)
 - groups [E.g. *ṛṇasamūhaḥ*, *jantusamūhaḥ*, *paśusaṅghaḥ* etc.]
- *vṛtti* (0)
 - profession [E.g. *ābhārī*, *vaidyaḥ*, *adhyāpakaḥ* etc.]
- *khādyam* (3)
 - eatable things [E.g. *grāsaḥ*, *bhuktocchiṣṭam* etc.]
- *nāma* (0)
 - names of the individuals [E.g. *bṛhaspatiḥ*, *śukrācāryaḥ*, *gaṅgā* etc.]
- *Vāhanam* (1)
 - vehicles [E.g. *krīḍārathaḥ*, *śakaṭikā*, *naukā* etc.]
- *vastram* (0)
 - cloths [E.g. *dhautakaśeyam*, *paṭṭavastram*, *uparivastram* etc.]
- *upakaraṇam* (4)
 - instruments [E.g. *kamaṇḍaluḥ*, *śarādhāraḥ*, *mūṣā* etc.]
- *ābharaṇam* (0)
 - ornaments [E.g. *śiromaṇiḥ*, *kirīṭam*, *karṇābharaṇam* etc.]
- *ratnam* (0)
 - gems [E.g. *maratakamaṇiḥ*, *pravālamāṇiḥ*, *hāramadhyamaṇiḥ* etc.]
- *dhanam* (0)
 - different types of prizes [E.g. *baḥiḥ*, *mūladhanam*, *rajatarūpyakam* etc.]
- *cihnam* (0)
 - signs [E.g. *rājacihnam*, *punḍram*, *viṣṇulāñcanam* etc.]
- *indriyam* (0)
 - organs [E.g. *śabdādīndriyam*, *caḅsurādīndriyam*, *pāyvadīndriyam* etc.]
- *kāraṇam* (0)
 - cause [E.g. *mukhyakāraṇam*, *sādhakatamam* etc.]
- *ākṛtiḥ* (0)
 - shape [E.g. *vṛttam*, *golaḥ* etc.]
- *śaktiḥ* (0)
 - power [E.g. *rājaśaktiḥ*, *siddhiḥ* etc.]

12 Conclusion

This extended NV ontology is emerged as a result of the application of NV ontology for building A-KN. This model is based on the classification of *jāti* and *upādhi* which gives scope for extension of ontology.

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A appendix - 1

Fig. 1. Vaiśeṣika Classification of objects

Fig. 2. jāti chart

उपाधियुक्तः

Fig. 3. upādhi chart